

OPTIMIZING SESAME CULTIVATION: a STUDY on FARMING PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during the *rabi* season of 2021, at Sambaravalli pudhur, Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu. The study was to evaluate the effect of different farming methods on growth and yield of sesame. The field was laid out in randomised block design with five replications. The treatments include T₁ – Organic farming with basal application of Farmyard manure (@5 t ha⁻¹) + Vermicompost (@1 t ha⁻¹) + Panchagavya 3% spray at 15 days interval, T₂ – Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) with Beejamritham seed treatment + Jeevamritham (@ 200 lit ha⁻¹) at 15 days interval + Acchadana (Straw mulching), T₃ – Conventional cultivation package of practices following TNAU crop production guide and T₄ – Absolute control. The findings of the study revealed that ZBNF, proved to be a beneficial farming method when compared to organic and conventional approaches.

Keywords: Sesame, white seed (SVPR 1), Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF), Organic Farming, Conventional Farming.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sesame, scientifically known as *Sesamum indicum* L., belongs to the Pedaliaceae family and is a significant and ancient indigenous oilseed crop often referred as the "queen of oilseeds," it is renowned for its high oil content, aromatic properties, and distinctive flavour [8]. It holds the sixth position among vegetable oils in terms of importance. The seeds are abundant in vitamins, minerals, protein, and fibre. Sesame oil is known for its high concentration of unsaturated fatty acids, fat-soluble vitamins, and amino acids. Sesame seeds contain 21.9% protein and 61.7% fat [9].

In India, traditional farming practices were inherently "organic" as they relied on minimal or no usage of chemical inputs. However, with the implementation of the Green Revolution in the 1960s, aimed at ensuring food security for the growing population, there was a significant increase in the use of chemical inputs. Unfortunately, this approach had adverse effects on the soil and environment. As a result, nations around the world, including both developed and developing countries, have been prompted to shift towards organic farming and the consumption of organic food. Thus increasing the demand for organic food products both in developed nations and in developing nations, leading to a hike in the price of these organic products. Organic inputs used as nutrient source to either soil or foliar serves as a soil conditioner along with raise in soil fertility by adding organic matter to the soil and achieve sustainable crop productivity. On the other hand Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) developed by Subhash Palekar, is gaining its popularity as an alternative to conventional farming methods due to its focus on sustainability, economic viability, and environmental conservation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted at organic certified field geographically located at 11°20' N latitude, 77°02' E longitude at an altitude of 426.7 m above mean sea level in Sambaravalli pudhur, Mettupalayam taluk, Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu during *rabi* 2021. The soil of the experimental site was sandy clay loam with organic carbon 0.8%, available N 204

kg ha⁻¹, P₂O₅ 55 kg ha⁻¹, K₂O 598 kg ha⁻¹. The experimental field plots were laid out in randomised block design with four treatments and five replications. White colour sesame seed variety SVPR 1 was used for the crop research. Uniform spacing of 30 cm between row and 30 cm between plants was maintained after thinning at 15 DAS and at 30 DAS. Appropriate crop production and protection measures were followed to raise a healthy crop. The experimental treatments comprise T₁ – organic farming practice with basal application of Farmyard Manure (@5 t ha⁻¹) + Vermicompost (@1 t ha⁻¹) + foliar application of 3% Panchagavya at 15 days interval, T₂ – Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) includes seed treatment with Bijamritham + Jeevamritham (@200 lit ha⁻¹) at 15 days interval + Acchadana (mulching with banana leaf), T₃ – Conventional cultivation package of practices as per TNAU crop production guide with RDF 21:23:23 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 3 packets of Azospirillum (600 g ha⁻¹) and 3 packets (600 g ha⁻¹) of Phosphobacteria and T₄ – Absolute control.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Plant growth parameters including crop height, root length, total dry matter production, yield and its attributes, as well as oil content, were observed, recorded, and the results are discussed.

A. Plant height

Among the different cultivation practice followed in sesame, significantly higher plant height was noticed in the Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) treatment (Fig. 1). Lower crop height was observed in control treatment. This increase in the plant height might be because of the periodic application of jeevamritham, which aided in the increased supplementation of the nutrients [4]. Naturally occurring beneficial microorganisms, including bacteria, yeast, actinomycetes, and certain fungi, have been identified in organic liquid manures these microorganisms play a significant role in supplementing the use of biofertilizers and biocontrol agents in crop production [7].

Fig. 1. Effect of different farming methods on plant height of sesame

B. Total Dry Matter Production

The total dry matter is the expression of plant productivity in terms of the dry weight of material produced per unit area during a specified period. From the observed results, it is evident that plants under the Zero Budget Natural Farming treatment produced more dry matter than the other treatments (Fig. 3). Statistically it is on par with the organic farming treatment in which FYM (5 t ha⁻¹) + Vermicompost (1 t ha⁻¹) + foliar application of 3% Panchagavya were applied. The control treatment

plants produced minimal dry matter because of lower plant height and less uptake of nutrients. An increase in biomass in *Amaranthus viridis* was noted as a result of increase in phytohormones such as IAA, Gibberlic acid, Abscisic acid and kinetin added from the organic manures [10]. Higher dry matter might be gained because of higher plant height and more leaf area. Similar findings were noted by Nileema, (2011) in tomato.

Fig. 2. Effect of different farming methods on total dry matter production of sesame

C. Root length

Root length of the crop at harvest stage was significantly on par between the treatments with FYM (5 t ha⁻¹) basal application + Vermicompost (1 t ha⁻¹) + 3% Panchagavya foliar spray at 15 day interval and ZBNF (Seed treatment with beejamritham + jeevamritham (200 lit ha⁻¹) at 15 days interval + straw mulching). Lower root length was noted in the control treatment (Fig. 3). Beejamritham provided protection to seeds from insects and diseases [6] at the initial stages of crop growth from which a healthy root establishment and root growth was observed. Similar findings were mentioned in root growth, total nutrient uptake and available soil nutrients [5]. Jeevamrita and bijamrita enhanced the mobilization of plant nutrients and increased the supply of essential plant growth-promoting substances and micro nutrients [2].

Fig. 3. Effect of different farming methods on root length of sesame

D. Yield attributes

The Zero Budget Natural Farming practice with Beejamritham for seed treatment + Jeevamritham foliar spray every 15 days + straw mulching led to the highest significant count of capsules per plant. Capsule counts across treatments varied between 113 and 96. The minimum capsule count was observed in the untreated control, yielding 96.0 capsules per plant (Table 1.).

The capsule length, number of seeds per capsule and test weight did not exhibit significant variation across different management practices accomplished for the sesame cultivation.

E. Seed yield

From the recorded data of the seed yield it is witnessed that the Zero Budget Natural Farming treatment was significantly higher (Table 1). In the concoction of jeevamritham a handful of native soil was added which, served as initial inoculum of microorganisms [2]. Hence, the higher number of beneficial bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, N-fixers and P-solubilizers helped in catalysing the transformation of nutrients into available form [3]. Furthermore, mulching with dried plant straw played a role in improving the yield by regulation of soil moisture and temperature as well in weed suppression, which lowered the crop-weed competition. A yield increase of 5- 11% was recorded with application of Jeevamritham to the crops [1].

Table 1. Effect of different farming methods at harvest stage on growth and yield

TREATMENT	PLANT HEIGHT (cm)	ROOT LENGTH (cm)	TDMP (kg/ha)	SEED YIELD (kg/ha)	NO. OF CAPSULE PER PLANT	SEEDS PER CAPSULE	CAPSULE LENGTH	TEST WEIGHT (g)
T1	137.54	20.47	3,222	801.9	109	60.4	3.12	2.91
T2	142.68	20.58	3,385	843.6	113	60.8	3.12	2.93
T3	132.90	19.68	3,061	732.7	103	60.4	3.11	2.90
T4	128.48	17.91	2,802	603.0	96	59.8	3.10	2.91
S.Ed	2.04	0.29	101.9	19.13	3.88	1.09	0.12	0.07
CD	4.41	0.64	222.2	41.70	8.45	NS	NS	NS

F. Economics

Benefit cost ratio was significantly higher in the ZBNF treatment because of the higher yield, higher net return and less cost of cultivation (Table 2). Among the treatments, cost inputs used during the crop cultivation is less in ZBNF treatment hence the net returns and the BCR is higher. Net return is 69.28 percent higher than organic farming treatment, 44.96 percent higher than conventional farming treatment and 58.66 percent higher in Zero Budget Natural Farming treatment compared to control treatment. Although the yield was higher in organic farming the net return was 16.74 percent lower than the conventional farming.

Table 2. Effect of different farming methods on economics of sesame

TREATMENT	GROSS RETURN (₹)	NET RETURN (₹)	BC RATIO
T1	96,235	31,285	1.48
T2	101,246	52,946	2.09
T3	87,925	36,522	1.71
T4	72,369	33,369	1.85

IV. CONCLUSION

From the study conducted to evaluate the difference between the different farming methods in sesame crop it can be concluded that the Zero Budget Natural Farming method can be beneficial to farmers in terms of high yield thus having higher net return and BC ratio. It is suited for farmers specifically for enabling them to improve their yields and livelihoods while reducing their dependence on external inputs. Incorporating these microorganisms into farming practices can have long-term benefits for enhancing soil fertility and promoting sustainable crop growth.

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